

Sounds of Climate Change: A Conversation between Sound Art, Data, and Alfred N. Whitehead

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Abstract: This paper develops a sonic approach to climate change. It argues that such an approach can help rethink political awareness of the climate crisis by engaging the vibrations that circulate between humans and the planet, affecting bodies on and below consciousness. To support this argument, the paper brings together Alfred N. Whitehead's process philosophy with climate data, sound art, and environmental political thought. In doing so, the paper hopes to generate new avenues for ecological thinking and information-sharing at a time when the effect of visual representations of environmental degradation is fading yet the need for sustainable living together accelerates.

Keywords: Whitehead, sound, climate change, vibration, listening, the Arctic

In 1962, Rachel Carson published her seminal work *Silent Spring*. In it, she ascribes the decline of audible birdsongs in springtime to harmful human activities (mainly the use of pesticides that kill birds), and calls for a renewal of ecological awareness.¹ Since then, silence has indeed become a central sign of the loss of biodiversity on the planet due to human interference, and Carson has turned into a key figure of the environmental movement.² But despite growing concerns over the earth's climate, Carson's initial intuition is often forgotten, and little is known today about the effective relationship between sound and climate change. In 2017, UNESCO appreciates that sound constitutes a key component in "the equilibrium of all human beings in their relationship with others and with the world,"³ yet it fails to notice that erratic climate patterns have made the experience of equilibrium the exception rather than the norm. Other global political agendas—like the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development—highlight climate change as "one of the greatest challenges of our time,"⁴ but pay no attention to the ways that it has significantly altered both acoustic environments and modes of perception.

More common strategies for communicating the effects of climate disaster rely on dramatic visualizations, such as Kerstin Langenberger's iconic picture of a starving polar bear which circulated the globe in 2015,⁵ or more recent images of the 2023 Canadian wildfires, paired with one of the countless data graphs of rising CO₂ emissions.⁶ Equally prominent is Al Gore's theatrical display in the film *An Inconvenient Truth*, in which he stands on a ladder to symbolize the otherwise unreachable newest level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.⁷ What these image-centered approaches share is the implicit hope that seeing the impacts of climate change will lead to a rise in ecological awareness and political mobilization. This hope builds on a longstanding tradition in Western thought that ties together sight and insight or knowing, vision, and truth.⁸ In effect, visual displays of information have not yet led to a widespread change in human behavior. Instead, they have created a situation in which growing numbers of facts, data, and images coincide with debilitating pessimism, apathy, and climate denialism.⁹

But even when we close our eyes, climate transformations continue to affect us below the level of consciousness. As political theorist William E. Connolly puts it, both social and human bodies have a "visceral" register, which shapes all political involvement.¹⁰ In the context of the climate crisis, this means that bodies react to environmental shifts—even without noticing. Often enough, such involuntary reactions or nonconscious reminders of entanglement induce great fear, spilling over into desperate attempts to take back control through increased securitization and destruction. In the most extreme cases, the distress over a loss of authority and livelihood is instrumentalized by neo-fascist agendas, which promote their own hostile program of exclusion, purification, and nationalism in the name of protecting the planet.¹¹ To counteract those attempts, it is vital to better understand the effects that material shifts in the environment have on the composition of bodies and political behavior. Even more pressing is the question of how ecological transformations, rather than undermining democratic responsiveness to climate-induced fears and inequalities, could actually strengthen it. If targeted visual strategies distract us from this task, it is time to explore alternative frameworks that consider the intuitive reactions we have to the places around us, allowing political awareness of the climate crisis to emerge from bodily sensibilities.

My paper argues that sound offers a path for such an exploration. I claim that climate change has a significant acoustic dimension, which indicates the various ways that bodies are interfolded with climate events. Instead of treating climate change as an external event, the paper will describe the climate as a set of existing relations between bodies and ecosystems. While I do not claim that this will solve the problem of collective action, the framing does contribute to conceptualizing modes of engagement that begin with the worldly forces that move the body to think and act.¹² By approaching these movements through sound, this paper will suggest that our thoughts, moods, and behavior already

connect us to the transformations that currently shape the planet. In doing so, I hope to open new avenues for sharing information about the climate crisis at a time when visual representations fail to affect people, yet the need for sustainable living-together accelerates. Moreover, I aim to help counter climate change denialism and eco-fascism, both of which wish to silence ecological entanglement. In short, I offer a sonic framework for studying climate change. Of the few studies that examine the sounds of the earth in recent years, most focus on nonhuman animals. Notable examples are Andrew Whitehouse's report on people's connection to birds in the Anthropocene,¹³ and Bernie Krause's prominent account of ecological entanglements as local concert halls for orchestras of plants and animals.¹⁴ While deeply appreciating these calls for explicit sonic attention, this paper takes on a wider material focus. It asks how, with shifting weather patterns, extinction of species, and ever-growing numbers of climate refugees, the soundscapes of the earth are transforming, unfolding effects also on the nonconscious register of experience.¹⁵ In this sense, my paper is aligned more closely with scholars like Stephanie Erev, who explore how increasingly irregular planetary movements create visceral accounts of climatic change below the habits of attention.¹⁶ However, despite sharing this sensibility to subterranean and volatile changes, the paper is not interested in affects beneath attention per se. Instead, it aims to approach specific moments when material change, nonconscious affection, and active bodily awareness meet. For this, I introduce examples of sound art that rely on the sonification of climate data to render audible ecological relations otherwise imperceptible to the human body. As Alexandra Supper contends, the sonification of data holds the promise of an experience of science that unites wonder with an element of terror.¹⁷ I take seriously that sonic vibrations unfold awe and fear in bodies, yet may equally connect people and environments in unforeseen ways. Listening to the pieces in this paper, I thus treat data as expressions of the earth and describe possible reactions in the receiving human body, using sound art "not only for documenting environmental toxicity but also for reshaping our very sense of time, place, and self as environment."¹⁸ To conceptualize interactions between "outside" forces and the body, I take inspiration from process philosopher Alfred N. Whitehead (1861-1947). Whitehead, I argue, offers distinct theoretical resources for bridging the gap between the conscious and nonconscious level or "us" and the "environment," specifically through his notions of "prehension" (the meeting of subjective and objective experience) and "feeling" (the joining of corporeal sensations and worldly data). The first section of the paper outlines the prospects and limits of Whitehead for a sonic account of climate change. Building on this, sections 2 and 3 listen to sound art pieces first on CO₂ emissions and ocean plastics, and then on springtime in the Arctic, situating them within research in environmental political thought, the environmental humanities, and an Inuit concept called *silá*.¹⁹ Section 4, eventually, discusses the political significance of sound for climate change research by relating sensory experience to material environments, and vast planetary currents to distinct times, places, and modes of awareness. With its sonic approach, the paper makes a wider, twofold

contribution. First, it calls to cultivate modes of awareness that make space for both active orientation and the not-fully-known. The paper thus embraces the role of nonconscious and material forces in deliberate political processes without negating human responsibility and addresses the future without resorting to simple predictions. Second, my paper emphasizes transdisciplinary dialogues, outlining the political impact of Whitehead's philosophy as well as the conceptual dimensions of data. Rather than recognizing the power of affect at the expense of scientific results, it thus treats data as participants in wider non-anthropocentric structures of attention. This endeavor also invites worldly events into thinking processes, following Whitehead's claim that creativity has both ontological and epistemological features.²⁰

To account for the coming-together of modes of creativity, I introduce a practice of "vibrational listening." This practice appreciates a deep connection between sound, vibration, and materiality. At the lowest threshold, each sound breaks down into palpable vibrations,²¹ emanating from a material source in motion. Some vibrations become audible, others not; few are consciously processed, yet all create reactions or "repeated physical sensations" in the body.²² Vibrations also change in tone and speed depending on the material they go through (like air, soil, or water). From a vibrational standpoint, sound thus crosses sensory and material thresholds. It renders audible "an intimate connection between the external world of objects in motion and an internal world of mental activity,"²³ eventually resisting the common distinction between experiencing human subjects and inanimate objects altogether.

Describing relations between humans and the sounds of their environments, soundscape scholar R. Murray Schafer prominently relates acts of listening to the human sense of hearing.²⁴ He specifies that this sense can never be closed off from the world, as the human body translates worldly vibrations into physical touch,²⁵ giving listening—in Deborah Kapchan's words—an affective dimension.²⁶ Schafer also claims that environmental sounds impress yet never threaten our hearing apparatus.²⁷ The era of climate change suggests otherwise, thus calling for modes of listening that take seriously the ways that disastrous and potentially harmful environmental events seep deep into human and nonhuman bodies. It further asks to treat the environment not as a neutral background or simple surrounding, but as "another constitutive link in the chains of mediation that make up the material and imaginative infrastructure of our lives."²⁸

Sound artist Raviv Ganchrow offers an impressive account of how human and nonhuman hearing is steeped in earth circuits. In lower registers, the human eardrum sways in motion, and acoustic and subatomic vibrations intermingle.²⁹ For Ganchrow, this means that the air that conducts hearing is not merely a medium for signals, but that ears, the vibrations to which they attend, and materials become coupled components in continually reconfiguring structures.³⁰

The challenge this account entails is to render audible earthly structures, yet also to let the vibrations that circulate between humans and the planet create translations between immediate immersion and more active political orientations.³¹ In other words, it asks us to speculate about a realm of experience in which nonconscious affection does not sit apart from deliberate listening attempts, but feelings, corporeal sensation, and evaluation become interwoven paths to the atmospheric shifts induced by the climate crisis. In this realm, we do not “pay attention” to the earth. We partake in acts of listening that allow awareness (of climate change) to reach from the subliminal to the conscious register, and to involve actual and potential scenarios.³² The next section will outline initial steps towards framing this realm, relying on Whitehead’s speculative philosophy.

WHITEHEADIAN SOUNDS

In his seminal work *Process and Reality*, Whitehead paves the way for a new tradition in philosophy, which finds the world to be composed of processes and movement. Instead of treating reality as either reducible to the “outside” world or only accessible through mediated sense perception, process philosophy is interested in the actions and feelings that take place in-between worldly bodies and entities. As part of this project, Whitehead finds it necessary to counter vision-centric thinking, complaining that philosophers have too often focused on “visual feelings” at the expense of “visceral feelings.”³³ While the former aim to represent events, the latter help to describe that which happens just “before” a moment occurs, or to approach those forces that inform the affective and emotional character of an event. To use Whitehead’s own language, a true visceral feeling constitutes a central component of the “conrescence” of a novel actual entity; it is “that functioning through which the conrescent actuality appropriates the datum so as to make it its own,”³⁴ or “the agency by which other things are built into the constitution of its one subject in process of conrescence.”³⁵ Let us unpack this.

Rather than establishing abstract substances as his basic metaphysical category, Whitehead finds the world to be composed of “actual entities” or “actual occasions” (his version of “things”).³⁶ Actual entities are “the final real things of which the world is made up.”³⁷ They have no content in the traditional sense, but a processual character, and are thus both completed in the moment and in constant change. What this means is that Whitehead introduces a temporal quality to things in the world, rethinking “substance” as a momentary formation that replaces the what of being with the how of becoming.³⁸ He then calls the process of becoming of an actual entity—the production of a novel togetherness—“conrescence”³⁹ or “ingression.”⁴⁰ In such a process, a potentiality inherent in an “eternal object” is realized for this specific occasion, or a pure virtuality creates the starting point for a new actual existence.⁴¹ As Whitehead says, “the metaphysical status of an eternal object is that of a possibility for an actuality”

or “actualization,” the latter being “a selection among possibilities” that become part of the actual entity.⁴²

The last phase of every concrescence is called “satisfaction.” This phase gives an actual entity its momentary final shape or particular self.⁴³ Important for us is that this momentary unity is felt. Or better, it is an aspect of feeling.⁴⁴ While a feeling initiates the concrescence or coming-together of an actual entity (as we heard above), it also stands at its transient end. And just like at the beginning, this “final” feeling is part of the world as much as it partakes in the perceiving human body. Thus, rather than being rooted in the subject or assembling subjective elements, Whiteheadian feelings are composed of impersonal forces or affective currents (although Whitehead does not use the term “affect” himself). Such a-subjective affective feelings create exchanges between bodies and the world or between the virtual and the actual register. In short, they are Whitehead’s way of saying that experience exceeds consciousness.

What is more, for Whitehead, feelings are always connected to data, by which he means any and all information provided to our bodies by the world. Every experience is one in which the world’s data are intimately felt and inflected. Thus, data are both real occurrences and “potentials for feeling.”⁴⁵ In the moment when an actual entity forms, a datum gains both reality and a specific feeling or affective tone. In turn, “[e]ach actual entity is conceived as an act of experience arising out of data. It is a process of ‘feeling’ the many data, so as to absorb them into the unity of one individual ‘satisfaction.’”⁴⁶ And while through this absorption, the “physical object is at rest, at least momentarily for its occasion,”⁴⁷ its data keep moving and unfolding. Whitehead captures this unfolding by claiming that each feeling conforms to the data, in that it feels the data. But the how of feeling, though it is germane to the data, is not fully determined by the data. The relevant feeling is not settled, as to its inclusions or exclusions of “subjective form,” by the data about which the feeling is concerned.⁴⁸

In short, data trigger modes of feeling-reception, but the latter are not reducible to them. While more and more scholars acknowledge data as moving agents in the world,⁴⁹ Whitehead goes a step further and uses the association of data and feeling to introduce a new subject-object relationship altogether. For him, a datum is the “objective content” of a feeling or experience,⁵⁰ which is always felt under a “perspective”⁵¹ and never in complete abstraction. Rather than presupposing a subject that encounters an objective datum—as so many traditional “philosophies of substance” do—Whitehead’s “philosophy of organism” assumes that subjective unity only ever emerges within the world when an event is met with feelings. It thus asks how organic data become part of a subject, so that object and subject are not final entities but shapes of feeling in the world.⁵² Phrased differently, data can neither be abstracted from objects

and subjects, nor are they determined by them. Instead, they become absorbed into worldly feelings that are shared by the “objectified” actuality and experiencing “subject” alike.⁵³

The effect of this process on the body is not “perception” per se but what Whitehead calls “prehension.” Prehension introduces the last dimension of feeling of an event; the moment when worldly data enter the composition of the prehending subject (“us”), or when feelings appropriate elements from the universe and give actual entities a “subjective form.”⁵⁴ This means that, in the event of prehension, the body neither apprehends nor perceives a present occasion but participates in a mode of feeling-analysis of actual entities driven by the world. A feeling-prehension is thus “not to be understood as an external response to an existing event. Feeling is what defines the quality of the event in the event,”⁵⁵ or what allows things to become built into the constitution of a subject through the process of concrescence.⁵⁶

This qualifying process also involves elimination,⁵⁷ since not every aspect of a datum or feeling can be prehended by a body in the same way at the same time. The specific constellation of data that a body can consciously sense through the subjective form Whitehead calls an emotion or “emotional complex.”⁵⁸ Philosopher Brian Massumi builds on this idea. He uses Whitehead to differentiate between affects (unqualified, a-personal intensities that relate only to the moving body) and emotions (qualified intensities that imply a purposeful evaluation of a situation). Affects make themselves felt in an “overfull” half-second delay in which “the body is radically open, absorbing impulses quicker than they can be perceived.”⁵⁹ Affects and emotions are thus folded into each other or constitute different invocations of the same forces, although affect retains some autonomy. As Massumi explains, Affect is autonomous to the degree to which it escapes confinement in the particular body whose vitality, or potential for interaction, it is. Formed, qualified, situated perceptions and cognitions fulfilling functions of actual connection or blockage are the capture and closure of affect. Emotion is the intensest (most contracted) expression of that capture—and of the fact that something has always and again escaped.⁶⁰

Altogether, a Whiteheadian feeling mutually constitutes a pure virtual force, a supplemental stage in which it is felt as emotion, and a satisfaction.⁶¹ Described in more linear ways, feelings start out as impersonal forces before gaining both an objective and a subjective element. Interesting for this paper is that Whitehead describes the constant transitions from worldly feelings to emotional character as movements from sound to music. To capture a-personal (material and affective) forces in the universe, Whitehead resorts to the sonic realm, mobilizing the term “vibration.” Specifically, he calls to “conceive each primordial element as a vibratory ebb and flow of an underlying energy, or activity,”⁶² contending that, in the history of metaphysics, “so far there has been no reference to the ultimate vibratory characters of organisms and to the

‘potential’ element in nature.”⁶³ Being made of vibrations, sound thus helps Whitehead to conceptualize those worldly processes that may be unnoticeable but nonetheless pursue and compose each thing and body, all the while composing the universe as such.

Through his own metaphysics, Whitehead aims to approach those potential or virtual—real without being actualized—processes that are folded into every concrescence. To describe the character of actualization or the specific modality that a concrescence takes on, he uses the term “feeling-tone.”⁶⁴ The term describes how worldly forces gain a specific identity, just as musical tones assemble sonic vibrations into more or less coherent formations. Through music, actual entities become sensible to the human ear and body to the extent that, for Whitehead, the audition of a note is again a form of feeling with both an auditory and a visceral component.⁶⁵ The “tone of feeling” is also shaped by the vibrations of eliminated data that remain in the background of every prehension even when they are not consciously perceived.⁶⁶

When Whitehead claims that all things are intrinsically vibratory, he makes not just a conceptual but an ontological claim about the nature of the universe. For him, vibrations set in motion processes of “natural pulsation”⁶⁷ that contain creative elements. Vibrational pulses can take on a more regular or irregular form yet always carry the potential for change. As a result, creativity becomes the fundamental principle of existence. “‘Creativity’,” Whitehead says, “is the universal of universals characterizing ultimate matter of fact,”⁶⁸ which suggests that every existence finds itself in a constant process of becoming, and that becoming is “a creative advance into novelty.”⁶⁹ Crucially, for Whitehead, this doctrine of the creative advance of the world is generally a positive fact. Today, when an increasing number of uncontrollable floods, hurricanes, and heat waves threaten the livelihood of millions of people, the experience of creative natural forces is not always pleasurable. It is especially devastating when changes in the atmosphere happen on a temporal scale that is either too gradual or too fast for us to notice, and when eco-fascist fantasies actively deny worldly creativity in favor of puristic ideals of natural beauty.

To describe gradual yet harmful effects, Rob Nixon has prominently coined the term “slow violence,” by which he means “violence that occurs gradually and out of sight, [...] an attritional violence that is typically not viewed as violence at all.”⁷⁰ But maybe it can be heard. Maybe sound helps us to become better attuned to ecological changes in time, and trains bodies to become aware in ways that involve and exceed sense perception. The subsequent section will explore how sound art engenders this mode of awareness by translating the data of climate disasters into musical tones. This sonic undertaking will go with and beyond Whitehead. Echoing Whitehead’s call for science and philosophy to be in dialogue with one another,⁷¹ my approach unites scientific data with Whitehead’s notion of sense data. In doing so, it turns the process of prehension

into a non-anthropocentric mode of feeling-attention, which attunes bodies to otherwise inaudible processes. This, I hope, will generate a listening space that is open for a variety of interpretations, while also introducing a sense of urgency to Whitehead's rather neutral attitude. So, let us hear what the world sounds like at the edge of extinction.

SOUNDS OF AIR AND OCEAN

Given fundamental shifts in the climate, sounds circumnavigating the earth today are taking about four times longer than they did in the earliest atmosphere (when they would have circulated the earth in less than ten hours).⁷² A central contributing factor to such atmospheric shifts are increasing CO₂ emissions, which leave traces in things and bodies and are recorded in databases, but are often difficult to describe. More generally speaking, atmospheres, in their constantly changing configurations, evade stable categories of experience. Massumi elaborates on the character of atmospheres as follows:

An atmosphere envelops like a space but lacks the definite boundaries and co-ordinate locations of spatial structure. [...] Its ability to pervade our feeling gives it an air of subjectivity, at the same time as it is experienced as being in the world, giving it a vaguely object-like presence. Space-like, occupying a gray zone between subject and object, the ontological status of atmosphere eludes the usual categories. However "heavy" the atmosphere, when we focus on its status, it melts into air, more sprite-like than "massive" in any usual sense of the word. It bears down without weight.⁷³

Today's atmospheres may have Massumi's "sprite-like" character, but they are not necessarily light or unnoticeable. Gravity waves occupy so much air on earth that they effectively gain weight in the atmosphere and fade into weather systems. Here, waves can extend thousands of kilometers and pressure cycles last and put stress on bodies for several days.⁷⁴

To tune into those cycles that are both elusive and violent, material and immaterial, human geographer Derek McCormack defines atmospheres as "elemental spacetimes that are simultaneously affective and meteorological," and whose properties can then be sensed through a practice called "envelopment."⁷⁵ Envelopment takes seriously that bodies are immersed in atmospheric milieus yet also generate methods to detect variations in that milieu.⁷⁶ I contend that envelopment can be approached through sonic parameters, as atmospheres are composed by the distinct assembly of material vibrations in a place. Vibrations reach from weightless subaudible rumbles to perceptible heavy sounds, enveloping things and bodies in equal measure. This section explores how atmospheric shifts can be a means for the earth to communicate and eventually even participate in artmaking. In that sense, atmo-

spheres constitute not just artistic objects but “the elemental art of the world’s surrounding and suffusing with potential.”⁷⁷

The Inuit communities in the Arctic regions of Canada and Denmark have already found a word for this potential: *silá*. *Silá* describes the climate, air, Earth, and atmosphere, as well as a distinct form of consciousness that is shared between humans and the planet. It is the “breath” animating all life, which human beings intimately experience through their own breathing bodies, and which asks people to live in balance with their inner and outer environments.⁷⁸ Indeed, atmospheres and the breath share an etymological history,⁷⁹ and even Whitehead describes the force that creates affective facts from data a “breath of feeling.”⁸⁰ In times of climate change, this breath is changing. With carbon dioxide and other pollutants filling the air, atmospheres become materially and metaphorically heavy, bearing on our moods, movements, and modes of existence. What is more, in many parts of the world, the world’s breath has become toxic as humans continue to erase the bacteria responsible for oxygen creation. Still, toxicity is unevenly distributed since richer nations offload toxins onto the world’s poorest countries or into the less affluent neighborhoods of metropolitan areas.

Appreciating the central role of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and climate change research, Chris Chafe, composer and director of Stanford’s Center for Computer Research in Music and Acoustics, has turned the global average temperatures and CO₂ levels in the atmosphere from 850 to 2016 into sound.⁸¹ His piece begins with a low buzz, accompanied by a sharp ringtone. In the 1700s, this soundscape begins to change, echoing the start of the Industrial Revolution and the era of deforestation and resource extraction. The intensification of those events is captured when the piece’s frequencies and ringtone increase in range and intensity up until the 1900s, when the ringtone becomes a high-pitched screech. The last few seconds of the piece are painful, almost unbearable to listen to. We are more used to observing this pain, or to seeing CO₂ data reflected in graphic representations. The sonic experience of the same data, however, does not stop at the eye. Chafe’s piece refuses to reach understanding through representation alone, or to reduce understanding to conscious perception. Instead, it allows us to effectively feel the changes in temperature and CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. And when the piece’s sound creeps into the air and our body, it induces a specific mood that echoes a Whiteheadian model of “positive prehension,” in which an item of concern becomes part of a subject’s (here: the listener’s) internal constitution.⁸²

As we know, prehension always implies interactions between a subject and a datum yet not necessarily consciousness. Sometimes, it even remains largely on the subliminal register,⁸³ signaling feelings that are “too small” or “too large” to enter conscious perception.⁸⁴ For Whitehead, consciousness only arrives late in the process of concrescence, namely when importance is given to

an event or object. This importance-giving constitutes a distinct moment in time but does not always occur voluntarily, and is mutually driven by body and mind. In fact, while bodies are part of every conscious act, mental processes can proceed without consciousness altogether.⁸⁵ What is more, contrary to the Rationalist tradition, which reserves conscious awareness for humanity, Whitehead thinks that conscious reflection might indicate the presence of a human being, but does not bring the human into being.⁸⁶ For our purpose, this means that every vibration or breath of feeling involves both conscious reactions and interstitial affects, and emerges from interactions of artists, artworks, data, and receiving bodies.

Altogether, from the point of prehension, atmospheres are not enclosed entities that surround humans, but complex sets of relations and exchange that submerge human bodies with new events in the world. As these relations are affectively charged, our perception of them—or sense perception in general—is never neutral. Listening to Chafe’s piece, it becomes obvious that prehension is not always pleasant, either. In fact, it may be uncomfortable or even harmful. When CO₂ levels in the air compromise life, the breath of the world can become piercing, and an atmosphere can become too heavy to bear. This experience is known by some more than others, creating a separation of what critical race scholar Neel Ahuja calls “carbon-fueled exterminations”⁸⁷ from “carbon-privileged bodies.”⁸⁸ Moreover, the inability to breathe due to toxins and dust particles in the air today also merges with breathing difficulties as a result of growing anxiety disorders and panic attacks, tying together social and economic pressures or the material exhaustion of bodies and environments.⁸⁹

Anxieties also unfold over diminishing water supplies and quality, since much of the warming breath of the earth has gone into the ocean. This has stopped temperatures from rising even more quickly. It has also caused some bodies of water to slowly dry out and others to expand, contributing to ever-rising global sea levels. Underwater, sound travels faster than through air, and even faster in warmer waters.⁹⁰ Water structures also change due to the disposal of waste in the ocean, acting as slow-release toxins for animals. Sound artist Jamie Perera’s “If the Oceans Could Speak, 1950-2050” draws attention to this by turning datasets of the production, consumption, and discarding of plastics in the oceans into audible sound.⁹¹ Perera thus creates another musical and visceral response to environmental degradation through the sonification of data.

Perera’s piece begins with a low rumbling or gurgling sound, increasingly disturbed by a scratching noise. The noise slowly breaks up the existing rhythm and moves the composition into a new direction. For Whitehead, too, “vibration and rhythm have a dominating importance in the physical world.”⁹² In addition to vibratory forces that Whitehead already linked to the “ebb and flow” of water before,⁹³ we now learn that the universe is traversed by a repeating “rhythm of process,” which allows us to discern “vaguely finite units of fact.”⁹⁴ With the

term “rhythm,” Whitehead thus describes how natural vibrations are in constant flux but also grow in complexity and introduce degrees of regularity. They establish somewhat stable relations between entities and modes of experience from the constant exchanges between virtuality and actuality, creativity and regularity, form and formation.

Listening to “If the Oceans Could Speak” with Whitehead in mind, we come to understand that vibrational becomings are creative but not completely arbitrary. Through repetitions of its base rhythm, the piece immerses us in its world and guides our perception. Then, just like the self-creative processes in Whitehead, the rhythm (un)folds into an increasingly complex harmony, accompanied by jarring sounds. As those grow louder in volume, we can more clearly identify that the rhythm that holds the piece—and maybe our world—together is made of the sound of crumpled plastic. And, over time, we grow accustomed to this sound. While the crumpling first emerges as a disturbance, it slowly weaves itself into the existing sound field, offering a new background tone of existence, or sonifying a new cohabitation of organic and inorganic materials on earth. This living-together and/as constellation of sounds eventually becomes so familiar that it makes the return to the beginning of the piece—a world without plastic—seem unimaginable.

To capture life as entanglement, many sound studies scholars remark upon the intimate connection of sound and water. Michel Chion, for instance, reminds us that humans first hear the sound of the amniotic fluid, and that all sound propagates in a circular, wave-like manner whose frequencies are measured in wavelengths.⁹⁵ R. Murray Schafer finds water sounds in all aspects of life (from birth to the flows of the unconscious), culminating in the ocean as the epitome of the multiplicity of Life’s rhythms.⁹⁶ Musical language also shapes the first underwater sound propagation experiments,⁹⁷ and studies of ocean temperatures using sonic indicators (so-called “ocean acoustic tomography”) are growing to this day. More specifically, changes in the structure of oceans are nowadays documented with the help of hydrophonic recordings used by scientists and government agencies to track whale routes, as well as undersea earthquakes and volcanoes. Oceanic surveillance has become so extensive that it leaves traces in both animal skulls (through calcium phosphate modulations) and modes of planetary hearing.⁹⁸

Contemporary composer John L. Adams goes so far as to state that life not only emerges from water, but transitions back to it again. “We’re made up mostly of water, and life on earth first emerged from the seas,” Adams says. “And with the melting of the polar ice caps and the rising sea levels, we may become ocean sooner than we imagine.”⁹⁹ Adams’ suspicion is met two-thirds through Perera’s piece, when there is a more noticeable break, possibly marking the time of the present. Afterwards, the sound of plastics dominates until, at the end of the piece, in the year 2050, waves take over again. Maybe we hear the effect of

humans finally making a change in their behavior. Or we hear the instant when humanity eventually becomes extinct, and oceans begin to restore their ecosystems. In the preceding moments, when this possibility reaches our consciousness, some unbearable sounds rush through our body, just like the sounds of CO₂ did before. Jointly, Chafe's and Perera's pieces thus carry us from the past to the present and future. Heard together, the pieces also sonify transitions between air and water that are integral to both the stability of earth systems and human survival.

Atmospheric transitions are in danger of collapsing across the globe. Moreover, while most of the cumulative CO₂ emissions released into the atmosphere are produced by nations in the Global North, they mostly affect the fragile ecosystems in places like the Arctic, where they have had devastating effects on the health of plants, animals, and people living there.¹⁰⁰ The next section will introduce sound art examples of Arctic data and soundscapes, focusing on passages between ocean and air and past and future. Rather than adhering to the more linear timelines that occupied this section, the subsequent artworks concentrate further on the intensities of the present moment, or on the complex temporalities and experiences of time associated with climate change.

ARCTIC SOUNDSCAPES

Crystallizing the fragility of transition zones and ecological exchanges, the Arctic occupies the center of many climate change discussions. It also constitutes a place where local knowledge of environmental processes is often subject to (neo-)colonial erasure. Appreciating this significance and complexity of the Arctic's ecosystems, this section listens to an atmosphere in which the dramatic changes that will characterize so many places on earth in the years to come are already audible. It thus moves from sounds of air and ocean in general to one specific place of life and political debate, asking what happens when the site that sets the scene for the breath of the world is melting away. Recording artist Jana Winderen shares Carson's intuition that fading sounds are noticed best in springtime. Her piece "Spring Bloom in the Marginal Ice Zone" unites hydrophonic recordings of water, sea ice, and animal voices in the dynamic border between the open sea and ice at the end of winter, which is ecologically extremely vulnerable.¹⁰¹ Before the main part begins, listeners hear the voice of climate scientist Carlos Duarte explaining the significance of spring in the Arctic. During that time, sea ice breaks up, and millions of algae begin to bloom, setting free microscopic creatures called phytoplankton. The algae then die and sink to the ocean floor to become food for under-water animals. This process is significant, as it initiates the largest carbon dioxide exchange on earth, responding to the accumulation of CO₂ that dominated Chafe's piece before. Phytoplankton capture about 37 billion metric tons of CO₂ (40 percent of all CO₂ produced) and contribute about 50 percent of all oxygen to our atmosphere.¹⁰² Evolutionary

speaking, the emergence of oxygenated water and air was possible only due to photosynthesizing algae.¹⁰³

In “Spring Bloom,” listeners experience the bloom of the algae, as well as the shifting sea ice that allows the carbon dioxide exchange to occur in the first place. The piece begins with a low gurgling sound and a melodious whistle tone that moves from a higher to a lower frequency while slowing down in speed. Repetitions of this tonal scale, alongside the sound of cracking ice, follow us throughout the piece. Soon, a gentle hum sets in, giving the piece an overall calm and soothing yet multi-layered character. “Spring Bloom” lets us appreciate an entire ecosystem. We hear the breath of the world. And the longer we listen, the more we notice changes to this breath. These changes happen slowly, with no or few sudden ruptures. As a result, we never doubt that we remain within the same soundscape or ecosystem. Yet our attention is drawn to its distinct constituent parts, generating a Whiteheadian sense of awareness that oscillates between background and foreground or present and passing (sense) data.¹⁰⁴

The feelings we inherit from this oscillation change as well, intrinsically linking bodies with environments, or the moment of audition with the event of recording, and both to the Arctic. We hear, as Whitehead says, that “[e]very actual entity is in its nature essentially social” as its character is shaped by its environmental data which become part of both the universe and the receiving entity.¹⁰⁵ In the event of “Spring Bloom,” this sociality creates a layered auditory experience in which ocean, organisms, and materialities develop modes of hearing, attention, and interpretation. Some eerie silences in the piece might remind us of early stories of the ocean as a “soundless” place,¹⁰⁶ or of the underwater “dead zones” that grow continuously as more and more fertilizers are dumped into the ocean after growing the crops for an ever-expanding global population.¹⁰⁷ The ocean’s response to this harm and exposure might be loud yet inaudible to the human ear, as well, as is evidenced by recent scientific findings of the small sounds that algae make during photosynthetic activity,¹⁰⁸ or of the frequent ultrasonic bursts that plants emit when they are under duress.¹⁰⁹

We then wonder if some of “Spring Bloom’s” low rumblings might not be residues of one of the hydrogen bomb tests that Chinese and Russian military are rumored to conduct in the Arctic. The explosive impacts of these tests destroy surrounding life forms and traverse in slow motion refractions through water, irradiating marine species, displacing islanders, increasing the likelihood of birth defects, and creating radioactive algae for the years to come.¹¹⁰ They also let immediate and long-term temporalities collide, or anxieties over climate change and ocean surveillance go hand in hand with renewed concerns over a nuclear arms race.¹¹¹ The rumblings in “Spring Bloom” might also stem from the deep-sea drillings and underwater bulldozing necessary for the extraction of oil. Political theorist Cara Daggett reminds us that every drill into the ground and our

nervous system is deeply gendered. It carries with it a distinct kind of Western “petromasculinity,”¹¹² which links the fossil fuel system to white patriarchal rule. And—as both Daggett and the uneasy sounds in Winderen’s piece tell us—threatening misogyny, the fossil fuel system, and the violence exerted on earthly materials will likely lead to even more brutal forms of climate denialism and gender anxiety, and potentially even fuel climate fascism.¹¹³

The rumblings could lastly point to the construction of undersea fiber-optic cables that are critical for today’s global network society. According to media studies scholar Nicole Starosielski, those cables are responsible for transporting 99 percent of all transoceanic communication.¹¹⁴ They also constitute an audible recollection of colonialism, as they were built along colonial infrastructure and trade routes,¹¹⁵ thus exposing both the historical roots of many ecological issues and the synthesis of economic and communicative power relations. Underwater communication is also significant for nonhuman animals, like whales and seals, audible a few times in Winderen’s piece. Whale songs gain specific significance given the substantial role that whales play in capturing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. As marine biologists have found, whales indeed accumulate CO₂ in their bodies and feed phytoplankton through substances in their waste products.¹¹⁶ The loss of whales is hence not just a concern for biodiversity but for CO₂ reduction, oxygen production, and the creation of livable space on earth. In that context, it is also significant that whales die more often today from a loss of contact and orientation due to faster-flowing sounds in warmer oceans that distort echolocation.

We, too, lose orientation when listening to “Spring Bloom,” just as we would in the ocean, where the density of the human eardrum is similar to that of water.¹¹⁷ When we do not know what we hear, we begin to speculate. Sometimes we identify wind among the waves; other times we suspect that the same sounds might stem from nonhuman animals. It certainly seems that the piece oscillates between soundscapes above and below the water’s surface as its sounds move from the right ear to the left. While this loss of orientation can be frightening, for humanities scholar Melody Jue, it encourages a rethinking of anthropocentric categories of thought and experience, which are usually informed by terrestrial movements or the force of gravity. “[T]he ocean,” Jue says, is “a material and imaginative space for the conditions of perception that we have taken for granted.”¹¹⁸

When perception is challenged, we search for new sources of orientation. In “Spring Bloom,” we find them in the recurring whistle tone which—like Whitehead’s feeling-tone—shapes our listening experience and experience of springtime. This reorientation goes so far that, by the end of the piece, water sounds have replaced our regular background sound of perception. The new background carries with it a distinct feeling of time in which the present moment is extended to and united with the past and future. Whitehead calls this prolonga-

tion of the immediate present a “concurrent unison.”¹¹⁹ In the case of “Spring Bloom,” it is a unison of multiple temporalities in and around springtime to the extent that we cannot be certain how many sonic layers we are listening to. We could be listening to various moments of one spring, condensed into sequences or stretched out in time, or to the springs of several years all at once.

Another play with springtime is offered by a piano piece of composer Judy Twedt. The piece traces data of Arctic Sea ice levels from 1979 to 2016 in musical notes, echoing the fact that oceans are increasingly composed of melting icebergs. Throughout Twedt’s piece, the left hand continuously plays four accords, capturing the four seasons in a year. The right hand replays the concentration of CO₂ and ice levels. When CO₂ rises in the atmosphere, the notes become higher. When sea ice fades, notes become lower.¹²⁰ The result is a piece that starts out in relative harmony and, by the early 2000s, fades into dissonance. After the first rendition, the centuries are traced through repetitions of the four-season chords, introducing the temporality of remembrance. In each musical spring, listeners notice variations in sea ice and atmosphere because they recall how the previous year sounded and fold this memory into the moment of audition. Each variation and/ or in memory also triggers a distinct atmospheric feeling and emotion, following the process of Whitehead’s prehension in which affective, corporeal, and material processes are shaped into consistent patterns of feelings.¹²¹

Whitehead is keen to notice that feelings are not born out of nowhere. Instead, a past that is relevant to a specific event becomes part of prehension (here: audition). Those can be pasts that were and pasts that never existed, like those in which the Arctic’s ecosystem recovers and harmonizes with the seasonal chords once again. Both pasts leave marks or “scars” on feelings. As Whitehead puts it, each feeling...bears on itself the scars of its birth; it recollects as a subjective emotion its struggle for existence; it retains the impress of what it might have been, but is not. It is for this reason that what an actual entity has avoided as a datum for feeling may yet be an important part of its equipment.¹²²

An emotion, in the Whiteheadian sense, is hence not simply a personal response to an event, but an eventful struggle through which a worldly feeling recollects its effort of coming into being. As every event is equipped with potentialities and unfinished paths, it creates a collection of what is, was, and could have been, and it remains connected to its multiple preceding and possible universes. Twedt’s piano piece introduces the struggles of these universes to exist into the present. While we—or better, our bodies—partake in the feeling-struggles of universes, the struggles as such usually remain inaccessible to us. “Arctic Sea Ice” allows us to experience them through repeating-yet-changing constellations of past and present, ice and atmosphere. The almost unnoticeable hesitations of the left hand before playing the accord of the next season let the listener sit in the “before” of a moment, which influences how the moment will

be experienced and emotionally responded to. It sounds as if the earth already knows more than we do. The barely perceivable accelerations after the accord is played then enhance the feeling of intimacy. Together, they introduce a mode of awareness in which immediate perception, anticipation, and remembrance meet, echoing Whitehead's conviction that novel formations in the world emerge from periodic accelerations of vibrations within and between entities.¹²³

Paying attention in this way also brings with it a sense of loss for the sonic constellations that do not repeat, or that we anticipated and hoped for but did not occur. Each missing accord recalls lost biodiversity and material richness. It further resounds the loss of local knowledges, mythologies, and modes of existence which—in the case of the Arctic—occur when local cultural practices are criminalized or the Inuit are forced out of their nomadic existence and into permanent settlements and wage labor.¹²⁴ In “Arctic Sea Ice,” we hear how the world struggles with such loss, introducing a sense of urgency. Urgency is felt when the melodies of the left and the right hand become increasingly dissonant. Then, dissonances fade into surprising harmonies, and the data of climate change become hauntingly beautiful. They recall the pleasures that the Global North enjoys as a direct consequence of destroying the planet. They also remind us that harmonic dissonance might become the new aesthetic and ecological standard in the future. The last section of this paper will engage in sonic speculations about this future, as well as the potential of nonconscious responses for political awareness. It will endure the silences that conclude both sound art pieces in this section—the fading crackling sound in Winderen, and the after-tone of the last note in Twedt—asking how they might signal the eerily quiet soundscapes on earth yet to come, and provide openings for affective forces to create moments of intervention.

SOUND DISCUSSIONS

In Whitehead's universe, the future never is. Better said, the future that will eventually be is not the most important thing to think about. What is important are the futures that Whitehead calls “relevant,” by which he means futures we expect or wish for and are hence filled with intensity in the present subject.¹²⁵ Such futures do not rely on predictions, but on the virtual possibilities that already exist yet are still inaudible. Massumi goes so far to claim that political possibility as such is born from this virtual realm; it is actualized potentiality committed not to subjectivist principles but the activity of the event,¹²⁶ eventually inspiring “a fundamentally noncognitive philosophy.”¹²⁷

What I have been interested in is not the potentiality of noncognitive faculties per se, but the space in between the conscious and the nonconscious register, or the moment in time that passes just before a thought or action takes place. My central claim throughout the paper has been that this affective realm expands the boundaries of the body, and that changes in earthly materials direct

the body with and without notice. Sound is particularly suited to approach those a/effects, as I have argued, as it draws attention to the nonconscious and material forces involved in climate awareness. As a flow itself that changes in different material atmospheres, and that manifests in human experience without terminating in the human body,¹²⁸ sound lives in border spaces or liminal temporalities. Listening to sound art, specifically, lets nonconscious elements seep into a body's conscious attention by uniting audible and inaudible vibrations or epistemological and onto- logical creativity.

For Whitehead, the human body is a “structured society.”¹²⁹ As such, it always gains and loses molecules,¹³⁰ and surroundings are constantly “poured into the living occasion.”¹³¹ It is impossible to define with certainty where the body ends and the environment begins; the body's demarcation from the “rest” of the world is vague at best.¹³² In this vague boundary realm, the body lies both with us and in the world. As Whitehead puts it, the body is “that portion of nature with which each moment of human experience intimately coöperates,” so that there is a continual “inflow and outflow of factors between the bodily actuality and the human experience.”¹³³ As a result, each experience is both mine and an experience of the world, and each event is mutually composed by the world and my body. This does not mean that experience is uniform or affects everyone in the same way. Instead, it confirms that we all have multiple centers of experience,¹³⁴ or that common and distinct encounters can meet. More politically speaking, sensitivity is both shared and specific to a place and the individual. Human beings all have nonconscious experiences whose distinct shapes are affected by social positioning and local soundscape. This idea of experience alters not just our understanding of sense perception but of thinking as such, countering the “disastrous separation of body and mind”¹³⁵ that Whitehead so often complains about. For Whitehead, each thought or perspective on an issue is not born from abstract reflection but constitutes the outcome of a feeling and thus vibrational (ex)change in the world. Even when entering the mind-body, thinking does not lose its feeling-character. A thought is only ever fully entertained when it is felt and hence both internalized and released back into the world.¹³⁶ Some thoughts exceed conscious comprehension altogether and remain on the affective register. What this means is that “there is always an understanding beyond our area of comprehension,”¹³⁷ and that feelings can become an embodied (conscious and nonconscious) mode of knowing or take on a subjective form called consciousness that combines physical and conceptual components.¹³⁸

As each feeling-perspective on the world constitutes an ever- shifting process of emphasis or abstraction of qualities, it carries with it a multitude of eliminated alternatives.¹³⁹ Every event or vibration felt in the body left behind others that were prevented from passing through a materiality or forced to go into another direction. Connolly explores ways to politically mobilize such non-taken pathways. He uses them—or the Whiteheadian “scars”—to detect “bifurcation

points” that invite “speculative forays” or “as if” scenarios.¹⁴⁰ Rather than simply postulating that nonhuman forces pursue thoughts and actions, as-if scenarios invite us to ponder what difference this pursuit might make for politics. What would happen, for instance, if we affirmed “that experience sinks far deeper into the biosphere” and acted as if “tectonic plates, ocean currents, glacier flows, waves at the seashore, and so forth are also inhabited by some degree of feeling and purpose?”¹⁴¹ Perhaps, Connolly says, it would be possible to appreciate entanglements of human and nonhuman forces and think of experiments to confirm them. An example could be the jazz and spoken-word piece “What If We...?” by composer Wendy Loomis and environmental researcher Alison Marklein, which combines an auditory graph of potential future sea-level rises with fictional news headlines that speculate how such changes might affect the globe.¹⁴²

Speculations also involve memory,¹⁴³ and data points unfold momentary feelings that can later be recalled. By remembering bifurcation points in Twedt’s piece, for instance, listeners return to states of the planet which, in a different arrangement, could have led to another accord or reality. Each data point also constitutes a chance for imagining other possible acoustic and ecological constellations on earth. Such speculations are not innocent. As Bruno Latour phrases it, in the face of climate disasters, speculative questions about the political are asked “again in terms of life and death. What am I ready to defend? Whom am I ready to sacrifice?”¹⁴⁴ Inuit scholar and anthropologist Zoe Todd warns us that answers to such questions often erase local laws and philosophies from discourse. According to Todd, it is easier for Euro-Westerners to save a symbolic polar bear than to respect Arctic Indigenous knowledge systems and socio-political realities.¹⁴⁵

The point here is that, when it comes to a future worth having, the wish to predict only gets us so far. Not being able to control or foresee events does not preclude us from participating in them. From a vibrational listening standpoint, the threshold for becoming involved in the world changes. We no longer need to establish connections to the environment. We sense that there is already a process of feeling between us and the world, and we think about ways to shape this existing inter-involvement. We remember that the breath of the world is already within us, molding our body—for better or for worse. So, what if we stopped trying to move and involve people and pointed out that natural vibrations in the biosphere are already affecting moods and actions? What if we knew that our bodies are already reacting to climate change, and that every reaction is shaped by the distinct ecological and social atmospheres we live in? The answers that sound offers are multiple, tracing possible futures back to the present moment. And they appreciate that some trajectories already exist, like the Inuit’s knowledge of *sila*, which adds an integral concept to the vocabulary of describing shared responsibility for life on earth.

A sonic perspective further affirms that possible solutions always have more than one author. Action is a concrescence, as Whitehead keeps reminding us, which means that humans participate in creative modes of experience yet are not the sole agents of creativity. This notion of creativity calls for openness and adaptability. In Whitehead's own words, an "unspecialized society" has better chances of survival when faced with changes in its environment, since it can adjust. A rigid society will find itself forced to either ignore unwelcome data or try to control novel elements.¹⁴⁶ Whitehead makes this point with respect to the human body, and the potential for corporeal openness and sensitivity was traced throughout this paper. Still, the paper also called to understand openness as pertaining to the wider societies we live in, whether in the form of flexible climate policies, open borders for climate refugees, or shared responsibility for biodiversity. Without space for the creative element, solutions will likely remain too rigid to address the ever-changing realities of climate change. With it, we may be able to become accountable for actions we barely sensed and never foresaw.

Whitehead goes on to explain that "however far the sphere of efficient causation be pushed in the determination of components of a concrescence [...] there always remains the final reaction of the self-creative unity of the universe."¹⁴⁷ Countless virtual potentialities can change every moment in time—just like the virtual tones that changed each accord or century in Twedt's piano piece. It is important to remember that virtualities do not render deliberate political efforts mute or inefficient. There is often a fear that appreciating self-organizing worldly creativity must go hand in hand with the loss of predictability and human responsibility. The very idea of unpredictability, however, constitutes "an epistemic screen"¹⁴⁸—a visual border—that separates us from the world and remains in the register of "right" and "wrong." Whitehead calls to forego the desire to create specific outcomes, and to instead mobilize creative relations that operate "by attraction and repulsion,"¹⁴⁹ and that already have effects in the world.

People react to these relations in many ways. My paper has appreciated multifaceted reactions by introducing listening to sound art pieces as a vibrational exchange between worldly expressions and various possible interpretations. In doing so, it aimed to inspire a dialogue about our intuitive responses to environments, and their wider effects. What remains is the question of how nonconscious experience can be actively affirmed, or how intimate corporeal matters may become public concerns. For Whitehead, every "concern" has both a personal and worldly, aesthetic and intellectual component.¹⁵⁰ It hence generates a new community of human and nonhuman forces, and places events into the experience of an individual or collective subject.¹⁵¹ Philosopher Erin Manning relates the concern back to the transition from sound to music, or to the affective tone produced with each actual entity. "This affective tone," Manning says, "is the concern—in Whiteheadian terms—for the event itself. [...]"

Concern is not concern for but concern with.”¹⁵² Avoiding a commonplace and distanced concern for the world, the concern-with realizes that shared goals and strategies emerge when events move bodies, and bodies draw inspiration from this movement. The sound art examples in this paper engaged in an active exploration of this process. They rendered audible how potentialities become actualized, thus tracing both past trajectories and the rumbling capacities of the next cosmic epoch.

What is at stake in this exploration is a shift in perspective from a romantic wish to return to the past in the future towards affective adaptation. Adaptation is possible because the sound art examples linked worldly data to currents of sensation that are both internal to the body and intimately shared with the world. The artworks made climate data approachable by reaching our mind-bodies or activating our affective as well as emotional register. In engaging transitions between body and environment for the experience of climate change, the artworks do not promote data as signifiers of Truth but allow data’s creative elements to trigger true feelings about the fact of climate change. Such feelings are “true” not in the traditional sense of the term, but because they have real effects on our behavior and are shaped by our social positioning, personal memory, affective experience, and material surroundings. Put differently, feeling-data are not vehicles of representation. But just like traditional representations, they are indicative of what is going on in the world.

Notably, sonic data and vibrations offer resources for tracing the affective beginnings of something new in the world, which we would miss if we reduced experience to sense perception. If violence is slow— as Nixon told us before— sounds that travel a million times slower than light, and are inflected countless along the way, are uniquely suited to trace and attune us to the fundamental exposure to the elements that is both natural and human-made, and that is always intertwined with dominant lines of discrimination. In other words, sound turns attention into a form of corporeal awareness that involves intersubjective yet also inter-material forces. Rather than directing attention in a given and singular way, it encourages a mode of participation that trains bodies to become more attuned. Or, as Ganchrow puts it, listening “to the expansiveness of earth-bound sound, through the [...] sloshing primordial oceans in our heads, may provide some provisional grounding in attentions-yet-to-come.”¹⁵³

Attunement can be dangerous, especially when today’s neo-fascists infiltrate our nervous system to co-opt nonconscious anger and anxiety in service of their own hostile project. In the most extreme case, eco-fascist fantasies turn attunement into a grand call for a purist harmony with Nature. In response, it might be time to think about ways to mobilize the openness of the affective register for modes of democratic awareness, or for imaginative democratic responses that take seriously the nonconscious elements in each normative commitment and institutional design. Such responses would treat the

environment not as an enclosed entity but as a complex set of relations and processes of exchange that both persist and shift over time. A sound framework begins to draw attention to these exchanges. At a time when visual representations and dramatic images of environmental degradation lead to information overload, such a framework establishes a more immediate (even if unwanted) connection to material environments, making us aware of the subterranean connections between today's social, political, and environmental crises.

To capture connections, Whitehead, as we know, resorts to the terms rhythm and vibration and their possible translation into music. Implied in this translation is the constant interaction between bodies and environments, and the idea that sound involves both in every event. The sound art pieces in this paper participated in these events— through the piercing vibrations in Chafe's CO2 piece, the vibrational patterns in Winderen's "Spring Bloom," the rhythmicity of plastic in Perera's composition, and the shifts in rhythm as well as vibration in Twedt's "Arctic Sea Ice." Taken together, the artworks capture unique ecological settings and layers of experience—atmospheres—in the world. Each atmosphere constitutes a distinct network of gases, liquids, entities, thoughts, emotions, and affects that is specific to the place it emerges from, and which shapes the actions of human and nonhuman bodies that populate it. In turn, every action is immersed in its environment, which is material as well as ideational and socio-cultural, and which engages local species, materialities, and structures of recognition in political outcomes.

To make outcomes ecologically sustainable, we frequently hear the call to listen to local experiences. From a sonic standpoint, the local reaches deep into the body and the materials of the earth. At the same time, it is always already global or reformulates the global as a planetary relationship. This reformulation neither initiates a forceful interruption of existing debates nor solidifies antagonisms. Instead, it lets local experiences, shifts in soundscapes, and planetary movements in tandem open up unknown connections, just like the conversations between sound art, science, and political theory have done in this paper. Maybe we can learn to listen to those connections. Maybe we can let them inspire new and—crucially—multiple strategies of political awareness-raising. Maybe we can attune our melody to the breath of the world and prehend already possible but still unheard-of relations to the earth and to one another.

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NOTES

1. Rachel Carson, *Silent Spring* (Houghton Mifflin, 1994), chapter 8. As pesticides were initially used to protect Elm trees, Carson's chapter points out the complexities and unintended consequences that result from rash measures in the context of environmental protection. The chapter also raises questions of responsibility and legitimate decision-making.
2. E.g., Mark Brown, "Environmental Science and Politics," in *The Oxford Handbook of Environmental Political Theory*, ed. Teena Gabrielson et al. (Oxford University Press, 2016), 495-96. Notably, this account of the environment movement discredits the longer history of environmental concerns and nonwestern sources.
3. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000247952.locale=fr>.
4. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>.
5. https://www.huffpost.com/archive/ca/entry/horribly-thin-polar-bear-revealed-in-kerstin-langenbergers-ph_n_8106620.
6. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/article/2024/aug/13/canada-2023-wildfires-nearly-decade-worth-blaze-emissions>.
7. *An Inconvenient Truth*, directed by Davis Guggenheim (Paramount Classics, 2006), DVD.
8. Lawrence Kramer, *The Hum of the World: A Philosophy of Listening* (University of California Press, 2018), 8.
9. Riley E. Dunlap, "Climate Change Skepticism and Denial: An Introduction," *American Behavioral Scientist* 57, no. 6 (2013): 691-98.
10. William E. Connolly, *Facing the Planetary: Entangled Humanism and the Politics of Swarming* (Duke University Press, 2017), 128, 167. For Connolly, this understanding eventually leads to more adventurous and effective modes of political action.
11. Sarah Manavis, "Eco-Fascism: The Ideology Marrying Environmentalism and White Supremacy Thriving Online," *The New Statesman*, 2018, <https://www.newstatesman.com/science-tech/2018/09/eco-fascism-ideology-marrying-environmentalism-and-white-supremacy>. In Internet forums, nature emojis are placed next to Proto-Germanic runes, and neo-Nazi rhetoric such as "lebensraum" or "blood and soil" is used to suggest that "homeland" needs to be reserved for the white species. The latter claim also translates into active calls for violence and ethnic cleansing through the hashtag #EFDS, an acronym for "Ecofascist Death Squads."
12. Along similar lines, Brian Massumi notably describes how worldly movements can activate collective expressions at the "infra-individual level" and without formal decision-making procedures in creative experiments (Brian Massumi, *The Principle of Unrest: Activist Philosophy in the Expanded Field* [Open Humanities Press, 2017]). As a result, collectivity moves past an aggregate of individual

actions and becomes an effective and embodied potential in the event, which both needs and exceeds the present individuals (139).

13. Andrew Whitehouse, "Listening to Birds in the Anthropocene: The Anxious Semiotics of Sound in a Human-Dominated World," *Environmental Humanities* 6, no. 1 (2015): 53-71.
14. Bernie Krause, *The Great Animal Orchestra: Finding the Origins of Music in the World's Wild Places* (Little, Brown and Company, 2012). Krause divides soundscapes into "biophony" (sounds generated by organisms), "geophony" (non-biological natural sounds), and "anthropophony" (sounds produced by humans).
15. Similar to N. Katherine Hayles's notion of "nonconscious cognition," I treat the nonconscious register as a collection of a body's immediate reactions to the environment. These reactions occur prior to conscious perception or recognition yet are still essential for consciousness to function (N. Katherine Hayles, *Unthought: The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious* [University of Chicago Press, 2017]).
16. Stephanie Erev, "Feeling the Vibrations: On the Micropolitics of Climate Change," *Political Theory* 47, no. 6 (2019): 836-63.
17. Alexandra Supper, "Sublime Frequencies: The Construction of Sublime Listening Experiences in the Sonification of Scientific Data," *Social Studies of Science* 44, no. 1 (2014): 34-58. Supper calls this the "auditory sublime."
18. Michelle Comstock and Mary E. Hocks, "The Sounds of Climate Change: Sonic Rhetoric in the Anthropocene, the Age of Human Impact," *Rhetoric Review* 35, no. 2 (2016): 166. As Comstock and Hocks argue for a place of sound in rhetorical studies, I aim to create space for sound in political theory.
19. Stefan Helmreich exemplarily unites research in the humanities and biological sciences via sound to argue that acoustics has a natural history, and all life is shaped by sound (Stefan Helmreich, *Sounding the Limits of Life: Essays in the Anthropology of Biology and Beyond* [Princeton University Press, 2016]).
20. Alfred N. Whitehead, *Process and Reality: An Essay in Cosmology*, ed. David R. Griffin and Donald W. Sherburne (Free Press, 1978), 4-9.
21. Shelley Trower, *Senses of Vibration: A History of the Pleasure and Pain of Sound* (Continuum, 2012), 1.
22. Trower, *Senses of Vibration*, 1.
23. Trower, *Senses of Vibration*, 2.
24. R. Murray Schafer, *The Soundscape: Our Sonic Environment and the Tuning of the World* (Destiny Books, 1977), chapter 14. Specifically, Schafer proposes to treat the world "as a macrocosmic musical composition" (5) in which humans take on the role of audience, performers, and composers (205). On a more general level, Schafer aims to establish soundscape studies or "environmental

acoustics” as an interdisciplinary research field combined of the natural sciences, social aspects, and the arts (3-4).

25. Schafer, *The Soundscape*, 11.
26. Deborah Kapchan, “The Splash of Icarus: Theorizing Sound Writing/ Writing Sound Theory,” in *Theorizing Sound Writing*, ed. Deborah Kapchan (Wesleyan University Press, 2017), 1-22.
27. Schafer, *The Soundscape*, 207.
28. Joshua Dittrich, *Geosonics: Listening Through Earth’s Soundscapes* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2024), 6.
29. Raviv Ganchrow, “Earth-Bound Sound: Oscillations of Hearing, Ocean, and Air,” *Theory & Event* 24, no. 1 (2021): 78.
30. Ganchrow, “Earth-Bound Sound,” 68.
31. Along similar lines, media studies scholar Joshua Dittrich sets up an approach of “transductive listening” (Dittrich, *Geosonics*). As both an “embodied experience and a technocultural act on a planetary scale” (19), this mode of listening is nonconscious yet not necessarily noncognitive (112).
32. Kapchan, too, defines listening as a speculative method (Kapchan, “The Splash of Icarus,” 4).
33. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 121.
34. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 164.
35. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 231.
36. E.g., Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 73.
37. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 18.
38. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 18-19, 166.
39. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 21.
40. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 23.
41. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 23; Alfred N. Whitehead, *Science and the Modern World: Lowell Lectures* (Macmillan, 1931), 228-30.
42. Whitehead, *Science and the Modern World*, 229. As a result, actual entities and eternal objects are the two extreme forms of existence (Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 22, 188-89).
43. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 26, 84, 154, 212.
44. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 26, 166.
45. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 88.
46. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 40.
47. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 321.

48. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 85.
49. Louise Amoore, for instance, claims that data are not just statistical objects but self-sufficient things whose power and agency alter security apparatuses (Amoore, *The Politics of Possibility: Risk and Security Beyond Probability* [Duke University Press, 2013]). For Amoore, data drive a new era of biopolitics by allowing even the most uncertain and improbable futures to be discerned as possibilities, thus creating a desire to control possibility as such.
50. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 150.
51. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 231.
52. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, xi, 3, 219. Specifically, Whitehead situates his process philosophy against both rational idealism and pure empiricism. He further claims that speculative boldness and systematicity must be combined with humbleness and experimentation, so that metaphysical categories do not become dogmatic statements but remain tentative formulations.
53. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 232-33.
54. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 19. Replacing the term “subject,” Whitehead calls satisfaction in this form “superject” to describe that which adds subjective character to worldly creativity (84, 166).
55. Erin Manning, *The Minor Gesture* (Duke University Press, 2016), 133.
56. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 231.
57. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 231.
58. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 41.
59. Brian Massumi, “The Autonomy of Affect,” *Cultural Critique* 31 (1995): 89.
60. Brian Massumi, *Parables for the Virtual: Movement, Affect, Sensation* (Duke University Press, 2021), xxxv.
61. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 212-14. A bit later, he claims that feelings can be divided “into five factors which express what that transition consists of, and effects. The factors are: (i) the ‘subject’ which feels, (ii) the ‘initial data’ which are to be felt, (iii) the ‘elimination’ in virtue of negative prehensions, (iv) the ‘objective datum’ which is felt, (v) the ‘subjective form’ which is how that subject feels that objective datum” (221).
62. Whitehead, *Science and the Modern World*, 53.
63. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 239.
64. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 119.
65. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 234.
66. Alfred N. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought* (Free Press, 1968), 89.
67. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 88-89.

68. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 21.
69. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 28. Real creativity does not negate the presence of a divine force. In fact, Whitehead speaks of “a world which is never the same twice, though always with the stable element of divine ordering” (31), making God’s purpose in creative advance the constant evocation of new intensities. For Whitehead, God is thus both a primordial force that introduces the principle of creativity and a creative power immanent to life that directs the vibrational material of the world in real time. God and the actual world conjoin in the creation of every novel concrescence, so that God does not constitute an exception to Whitehead’s metaphysical principle of creativity (105, 111, 245, 343, 348).
70. Rob Nixon, *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor* (Harvard University Press, 2011), 2, my emphasis.
71. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 91; Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 172. So far, Whitehead says, philosophy has been misled by a wrong application of mathematics with the unfortunate effect of static dogmatism.
72. Ganchrow, “Earth-Bound Sound,” 75.
73. Brian Massumi, *Couplets: Travels in Speculative Pragmatism* (Duke University Press, 2021), 189.
74. Ganchrow, “Earth-Bound Sound,” 103.
75. Derek P. McCormack, *Atmospheric Things: On the Allure of Elemental Envelopment* (Duke University Press, 2018), 4. McCormack uses envelopment also as a way of bridging speculative realism and materialism. Chapter 6 of his book focuses on sound, as well.
76. McCormack, *Atmospheric Things*, 4-6.
77. Massumi, *Couplets*, 204.
78. Janet T. McGrath, “Sila,” in *An Ecotopian Lexicon*, ed. Matthew Schneider-Mayerson and Brent R. Bellamy (University of Minnesota Press, 2019), 256-65; Timothy B. Leduc, “Sila Dialogues on Climate Change: Inuit Wisdom for a Cross-Cultural Interdisciplinarity,” *Climate Change* 85 (2007): 237-50. It is noteworthy that Indigenous terms cannot be easily translated into English without losing part of their specific cultural meaning (George E. Tinker, “Community and Ecological Justice: A Native American Response,” in *Earth at Risk: An Environmental Dialogue between Religion and Science*, ed. Donald B. Conroy and Rodney L. Petersen [Humanity Books, 2000], 239-58).
79. David Macauley, *Elemental Philosophy: Earth, Air, Fire, and Water as Environmental Ideas* (State University of New York Press, 2010), 29-30.
80. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 85.

81. <https://www.kqed.org/science/1918660/listen-1200-years-of-earths-climate-transformed-into-sound>. The data were collected by the three UC Berkeley graduate students Hal Gordon, Kate Pennington, and Valeri Vasquez.
82. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 41. "Negative prehension," by contrast, excludes that item from the internal constitution of the subject.
83. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 19, 23.
84. Massumi, *Parables for the Virtual*, 17.
85. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 85.
86. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 53-54, 62. The status of the human remains ambiguous in Whitehead. On the one hand, he resists anthropocentrism and finds the difference between animals, vegetables, and humans to be in degree, not kind (119). On the other hand, his thinking exhibits residues of human exceptionalism, describing humans as "higher animals" due their ability to introduce novelty in the world (which includes the power of imagination and action) (Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 30). The exceptional status of humanity also informs Whitehead's notion of ideas as the "essence of civilization" (3), or of language as "the triumph of human ingenuity" (31) and the final result of "civilizational advance" (35).
87. Neel Ahuja, "Intimate Atmospheres: Queer Theory in a Time of Extinctions," *GLQ: A Journal of Lesbian and Gay Studies* 21, no. 2-3 (2015): 367.
88. Ahuja, "Intimate Atmospheres," 375.
89. Jussi Parikka, *A Geology of Media* (University of Minnesota Press, 2015), 107.
90. Michel Chion, *Sound: An Acoulogical Treatise* (Duke University Press, 2016), 17; Stefan Helmreich, "An Anthropologist Underwater: Immersive Soundscapes, Submarine Cyborgs, and Transductive Ethnography," *American Ethnologist* 34, no. 4 (2007): 628.
91. <https://www.jamieperera.com/climate-data-sonification>. The data are derived from the World Economic Forum, Plastics Europe, the University of California Santa Barbara, the University of Georgia, and Sea Education Association in Massachusetts. Perera's piece was first exhibited at Toronto's Design Exchange in 2017.
92. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 277.
93. Whitehead, *Science and the Modern World*, 53.
94. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 88.
95. Chion, *Sound*, 12-13, 18.
96. Schafer, *The Soundscape*, 15, 18, 170. Different water sounds and their literary descriptions are discussed mainly in chapter 1 of the book.
97. Helmreich, *Sounding the Limits of Life*, 140. Helmreich distinguishes between three modes of music meeting water; music can evoke water symbolically,

invoke water as a material instrument or sonic element, and soak in water when it is performed or recorded in actual water (138).

98. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 98.
99. <https://cantaloupe-music.com/albums/become-ocean>. With this statement, Adams also explains the relevance of his piece "Become Ocean."
100. Mark Nuttall and Terry V. Callaghan, "Introduction," in *The Arctic: Environment, People, Policy*, ed. Mark Nuttall and Terry V. Callaghan (Routledge, 2000), xxvii.
101. <https://www.janawinderen.com/releases/spring-bloom-in-the-marginal-ice-zone>. The piece was first exhibited at the Sonic Acts festival in Amsterdam in 2017. My analysis relies on the Headphones version of the piece.
102. Ralph Chami et al., "Nature's Solution to Climate Change: A Strategy to Protect Whales Can Limit Greenhouse Gases and Global Warming," *Finance & Development* (December 2019), <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/2019/12/natures-solution-to-climate-change-chami>.
103. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 73-74.
104. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 89.
105. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 203.
106. Helmreich, *Sounding the Limits of Life*, 138.
107. Jan Zalasiewicz and Mark Williams, *Ocean Worlds: The Story of Seas on Earth and Other Planets* (Oxford University Press, 2014), 183.
108. <https://www.livescience.com/64207-photosynthesis-makes-ping-sound-underwater.html>. The finding that algae emit sounds while carrying out photosynthesis is the result of a recent study of the U.S. Naval Undersea Warfare Center in Rhode Island.
109. The study was undertaken by a research group at Tel Aviv University. It found that, when thirsty or recently cut, plants emit high frequency popping sounds much more frequently than under regular conditions (Itzhak Khait et al, "Sounds Emitted by Plants Under Stress are Airborne and Informative," *Cell* 186, no. 7 [2023]: 1328-36). The plants' sounds can be detected up to five meters away, escape human hearing, and differ depending on the cause of stress. <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/discover/news/2023/april/plants-emit-ultrasonic-popping-sound-when-stressed.html>; <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2023/mar/30/plants-emit-ultrasonic-sounds-in-rapid-bursts-when-stressed> scientists-say.
110. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 92-94.
111. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 100.
112. Cara Daggett, "Petro-Masculinity: Fossil Fuels and Authoritarian Desire," *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 47, no. 1 (2018): 25-44.

113. Daggett, "Petro-Masculinity," 43-44.
114. Nicole Starosielski, *The Undersea Network* (Duke University Press, 2015), 1.
115. Starosielski, *The Undersea Network*, 12, 30-37.
116. Chami et al., "Nature's Solution to Climate Change."
117. Nina S. Eidsheim, *Sensing Sound: Singing & Listening as Vibrational Practice* (Duke University Press, 2015), 45.
118. Melody Jue, *Wild Blue Media: Thinking Through Seawater* (Duke University Press, 2020), 3.
119. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 124-25.
120. <https://crosscut.com/2018/12/when-turned-music-climate-change-sounds-alarmingly-beautiful>.
121. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 89, 166.
122. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 226-27.
123. William E. Connolly, *The Fragility of Things: Self-Organizing Processes, Neoliberal Fantasies, and Democratic Activism* (Duke University Press, 2013), 156.
124. Frederic Laugrand, "Arctic Ontology on the Ice: Inuit Traditions, Ecology, and the Problem of Categories," in *Routledge Handbook of Religion and Ecology*, ed. Willis Jenkins, Mary E. Tucker, and John Grim (Routledge, 2016), 148.
125. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 27.
126. Massumi, *Couplets*, 69.
127. Brian Massumi, *Semblance and Event: Activist Philosophy and the Occurrent Arts* (MIT Press, 2011), 6.
128. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 70.
129. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 99.
130. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 160-61.
131. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 339.
132. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 160-61.
133. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 115.
134. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 163-64.
135. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 246.
136. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 153. Explanations are hence always incomplete and reliant on exchanges between empirical observations and imaginative generalizations.
137. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 42.

138. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 241-43.
139. Whitehead, *Modes of Thought*, 66-67, 108.
140. Connolly, *Facing the Planetary*, chapter 3. In addition to Whitehead, Connolly relies on Kant, Deleuze, and Nietzsche to explore such speculative forays.
141. Connolly, *Facing the Planetary*, 116.
142. <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/11/09/science/climate-change-music-sound.html>.
143. Connolly, *Facing the Planetary*. 80.
144. Bruno Latour, *Facing Gaia: Eight Lectures on the New Climatic Regime* (Polity Press, 2017), 227.
145. Zoe Todd, "An Indigenous Feminist's Take on the Ontological Turn: 'Ontology' Is Just Another Word for Colonialism," *Journal of Historical Sociology* 29, no. 1 (2016): 6.
146. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 100-2.
147. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 47.
148. Connolly, *The Fragility of Things*, 157.
149. Connolly, *The Fragility of Things*, 158.
150. Whitehead, *Process and Reality*, 212-14. This process is also called "appetition."
151. Steve Goodman, *Sonic Warfare: Sound, Affect, and the Ecology of Fear* (MIT Press, 2010), 92.
152. Erin Manning, *Relation-scapes: Movement, Art, Philosophy* (MIT Press, 2012), 40, my emphasis.
153. Ganchrow, "Earth-Bound Sound," 108.